
AWARENESS ON THE USE OF SPICES AMONG WOMEN IN THE ANTENATAL AND POST PARTUM PERIOD IN IBADAN, OYO STATE.

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of a study on the knowledge and use of spices among women in the various stages of pregnancy (antenatal) and immediately after delivery (Postpartum). This was aimed at gathering baseline information on utilization of spices amongst various consumer groups in Ibadan, Oyo State. One hundred respondents (100) made up of women from both categories were interviewed in the antenatal and postnatal clinics of the University College Hospital, Ibadan using well structured interview schedule as the means for data collection. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and chi-square test. The study revealed that majority of the respondents (65%) were between the ages of 31-50years and 95% were married. About 93% had one formal education or the other and average household size among the women was 82% of 1-4 people (category). The spices mostly utilized for health purposes among women in the ante and post periods respectively were *Occimum gratissimum* and garlic while onion and *Parkia biglobosa* were used on the basis of flavour. The chi square results showed that the variables age, education and level of income of respondents were socio-economic factors that influenced the awareness on the use of spices amongst women in both antenatal and postpartum periods.

KEYWORDS: Antenatal, Postpartum, Health purposes and Spices

INTRODUCTION

In traditional societies, nutrition and health care are interconnected hence many plants are consumed both for food and health benefits (Etkin, 1996).

Interest in the role of antioxidants in human health has prompted research in the fields of food science and horticulture to access fruit and vegetable antioxidants (Kalt *et al*, 1999).

Native plant species are used for daily diet in Nigeria as vegetables, spices and condiments. Spices and herbs are recognized as sources of natural antioxidants that can protect from oxidative stress and thus play an important role in the chemoprevention of diseases that have their etiology and pathophysiology in reactive oxygen species (Velioglu *et al*; 2003)

Spices have played an essential part in the development of human civilization. They are used as food preservatives and for medicinal purposes in aromatherapy, in addition to their uses in the cosmetic industry. Examples of these spices include clove, chili/pepper, garlic, onions and ginger which are classified as exotic spices and *Monodora myristica*, *Piper guineenses*, *Xylophia aethiopica* among others which are classified as indigenous spices.

Most of the spices have medicinal and nutritional uses ranging from treatment of cough, pneumonia, appetite boosters, womb cleansing and several others.

Women in the antenatal and post partum period are basically referred to as pregnant women and women who have just been delivered of their babies respectively.

Antenatal period is the interval from conception to the delivery of the fetus (ABC of Antenatal Care, 1997). The need for a balanced diet during pregnancy forms part of the health education talk at every antenatal visit.

Ideally, the diet should contain adequate amount of nutrients such as carbohydrates, protein, fats, mineral salts, water and spices to help boost the immune system.

In the Southern part of Nigeria, many of the spices and condiments are collected from the wild. These spices and their herbs are used generally to prepare “pepper soups” which may be taken hot or cold especially during the cold, rainy seasons. Achinewu, *et al* (1995) reported that these spices are particularly very important in the diets of post-partum women as an aid to the contraction of the uterus (which had expanded during pregnancy).

The postnatal period (or called postpartum) is defined as the period beginning one hour after the delivery of the placenta and continuing until six weeks (42 days) after the birth of an infant (WHO, 1998). Care during this period is critical for the health and survival of both the mother and the newborn (Lawn J and Kerber K: 2006). The postpartum dietary and lifestyle habits vary greatly among different countries and cultures (Morris, 1999). In western countries instead of restrictions, women are encouraged to eat well balanced diet from all food categories and start physical exercises during this period (Artal, 2003)

Recent estimates show that 25.4 million children suffer from clinical and marginal vitamin A deficiency, while 2.2 billion people, mainly children and pregnant women suffer from iron deficiency anemia (World Bank, 1994). Similarly, a recent survey report in Nigeria showed that at the national level, 24.8% of children under 5 suffered from subclinical vitamin A deficiency while 4.7% were vitamin A deficient, making a total of 29.5% who suffered from clinical deficiency. In the women, 13.1% of mothers and 19.2% of pregnant women were at risk of vitamin A deficiency (IITA, 2004).

Literature has shown that most of these spices have not only some economic values but medicinal and nutritional properties. It therefore becomes imperative to access the knowledge and use of these spices amongst women in the antenatal and post-partum periods in Ibadan, Oyo State with a view to generating baseline information on the consumption of spices amongst these vulnerable groups. Thus furnishing extension agents with relevant information on the awareness and use of spices mostly among women and thus enabling them adopt strategies in reaching both producers and consumers of spices in Southwestern Nigeria.

The following specific objectives were considered in the course of this study:

- To determine the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents
- To assess the awareness and use of spices among women in the Antenatal and Post partum periods
- To identify the socio-economic factors that influence the knowledge and use of these spices among both groups of women.

Hypothesis – the following hypothesis was tested:

HO: Socio-economic characteristics of women in the antenatal and postpartum period have no significant relationship with their knowledge and use of spices.

HA: Socio-economic characteristics of women in the antenatal and postpartum period have a significant relationship with their knowledge and use of spices.

METHODOLOGY

Ibadan, the capital of Oyo State, is the largest city in Nigeria. It is located in the South-Western part of the Country. There are 11 local government areas (5 within the metropolis and 6 in the outskirts) in the state.

The study was carried out at the University College Hospital, Ibadan. One hundred (100) respondents covering fifty women in the antenatal and fifty in the post partum periods were randomly selected in the antenatal and post-partum clinics respectively.

Well-structured questionnaires and interview schedule formed the means of data collection. Data collected include socio-economic status, awareness and use of spices and the basic reasons for usage. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics to determine the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents and chi-square test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The socio-economic characteristics of the respondents as shown in table 1. for both the antenatal and postpartum periods respectively, have majority (65%) of the respondents in both categories between the ages of 31-50 years.

An appreciable number (95%) of the respondents in both cases were married which could be explained the mean age bracket of the women and their inclusion in either categories (antenatal/postpartum).

73% of the women were Christians and averagely 93% of the respondents had one formal education or the other. The study also revealed that 82% of the respondents in both antenatal and postpartum periods had an average family size of 1-4 and the most predominant ethnic group was the Yoruba tribe (92%) which could be as a result of the study area.

About (50%) were self employed in one business enterprise or another while (42%) were salary earners and (8%) were unemployed. The average household income of 67% of the women sampled was highest in the range N10, 000- ₦70, 000.

Assessment of the Knowledge and Use of Spices

Fig.1 and 2 revealed knowledge and use of spices amongst women in the antenatal and postpartum periods respectively.

Amongst women in the antenatal period, *Occimum gratissimum* was rated highest (48%) as spices mostly used for health purposes while onion ranked least with 22%. As flavouring, the reverse was the case with onion ranking highest at 38% and *Occimum gratissimum* being the least used at 10%.

For women in the postpartum period, garlic spice was mostly used for health purposes (38%) while *Occimum gratissimum* and *Parkia biglobossa* tied with the least position at (18%) respectively. As flavouring, *Parkia biglobossa* ranked highest (52%) while *Occimum gratissimum* ranked least with 12%.

Literature has shown that onion is an antibiotic as well as an anti-diabetic spice (Pamplone-Roger, 1999). While Antonio et al 1982, has shown that *Parkia biglobossa* is highly nutritious containing about 54% fat and 30% protein (of good qualities) in addition to vitamins and minerals. Also, Ogbe et al, (2009) in their study found out that ethno-medicines are used for a range of female reproductive conditions in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State, including some of the direct causes of maternal mortality in Nigeria. They found out that some spices were used for certain conditions in pregnancy, at delivery and the post-partum period. Dried ground seeds of *Aframomum sceptrum* K. Schum, was discovered to be applied topically to prevent miscarriages in pregnancy as well as *Ocimum gratissimum* which is applied to the lower portion of the abdomen for the same purpose. In cases of prolonged labour, *Aframomum sceptrum* seeds are chewed with roots of *Carica papaya*. The study also found out that the problem of reduced lactation in the post-partum period is controlled using *Ocimum gratissimum* leaves cooked in soup.

Moreover, *Piper guineense* is an important medicinal plant, and it is used to treat gonorrhoea. The leaves, eaten in soups, are thought to assist conception in women and this has also been reported by Addae-Mensah (1992) in Ghana.

Socio-Economic Characteristics of Women in the Antenatal and Post-Partum Periods Vis-À-Vis Their Knowledge and Use of Spices.

The result according to Table 1 showed that the variables age, education and level of income of respondents were socio-economic factors that influenced the knowledge and use of spices amongst women in the antenatal and postpartum periods respectively.

The age and educational status had a high level significance on awareness and use of spices and this could be explained by the fact that most of the women are still young, mentally alert and quite enlightened to the nutritional and medicinal properties of the spices.

The level of income of the respondents which had a significant influence on spices usage could be explained by the consumers' theory which states that the higher the income earned the higher the propensity to consume spices and vice-versa.

However, marital status, religion, family size, ethnicity and occupation were socio-economic variables that did not influence the knowledge and use of spices among the respondents in both categories.

Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted which states that: Socio-economic characteristics of women in the antenatal and postpartum

Period have a significant relationship with their knowledge and use of spices.

CONCLUSION

From the study, women in the antenatal period preferably used *Occimum gratissimum* and onions while women in the postpartum periods prominently used garlic and *Parkia biglobossa* more than any other spice. This therefore calls for an enlightenment campaign to eradicate the poor adoption of spices consumption and highlight their medicinal and nutritional benefits amongst this people group and the society at large.

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Fig. 1 Preferential Spices by women in the Antenatal Period

Fig. 2 Preferential Spices by women in the Postpartum Period

Table 1: Socio-Economic Characteristics Of Women In The Antenatal And Postpartum Period Respectively Showing The Factors Which Influence The Knowledge And Use Of Spices Amongst The Respondents.

Variable	Antenatal %	Postpartum %	Total Average %	Coefficients	Df	P-Value
Age				8.319 ^a	2	0.016*
<18 yrs	2.0	0	1.0			
18-30 yrs	38.0	30.0	34.0			
31-50 yrs	60.0	70.0	65.0			
Marital				0.651 ^b	1	0.420
Single	4.0	6.0	5.0			
Married	96.0	94.0	95.0			
Religion				0.550 ^b	1	0.458
Christianity	70.0	76.0	73.0			
Islam	30.0	24.0	27.0			
Education				14.605 ^a	4	0.006*
Primary	10.0	2.0	6.0			
Secondary	28.0	22.0	25.0			
Tertiary	54.0	70.0	62.0			
Non-formal	6.0	0	3.0			
Illiterate	2.0	6.0	4.0			
Family size				2.713 ^a	2	0.258
1-4	82.0	82.0	82.0			
5-9	16.0	18.0	17.0			
10-15	2.0	0	1.0			
Ethnicity				1.075 ^a	3	0.783
Yoruba	90.0	94.0	92.0			
Igbo	10.0	2.0	6.0			
Hausa	0	2.0	1.0			
Others	0	2.0	1.0			
Occupation				2.096 ^a	2	0.351
Salary earners	36.0	48.0	42.0			
Self-employed	58.0	42.0	50.0			
None	6.0	10.0	8.0			
Household income				10.608 ^a	5	0.060*
<₦10,000	20.0	18.0	19.0			
₦10,000-70,000	64.0	70.0	67.0			
₦71,000-120,000	4.0	2.0	3.0			
>₦120,000	4.0	2.0	3.0			
None	8.0	8.0	8.0			

Source: Field survey 2010

*(Significant at 5%)

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